

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Talaei, B. (2016), Ketenes as Privileged Synthons in the Synthesis of Heterocyclic Compounds Part 3. Six-Membered Heterocycles, Journal of Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry, 118, [doi:10.1016/bs.aihch.2015.10.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aihch.2015.10.007)

Ketenes as Privileged Synthons in the Synthesis of Heterocyclic Compounds Part 3. Six-Membered Heterocycles

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Bahareh Talaei

¹Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Ketenes are mostly used as common starting materials for structurally diverse mono-, spiro- and fused six-membered heterocycles such as lactones, pyrans, pyronones, pyridines, quinolines, isoquinolines, oxazine, quinoxalines, thiazines, oxathines, etc.

Keywords

Isoquinolines, Ketenes, Thiazines, Oxathines, Oxazine, Pyrans, Pyridines, Pyronones, Quinolines, Quinoxalines